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THEMES AS BRIDGES BETWEEN PROBLEM AND SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

Expert designers are known to frame the problems they are confronted with in new and interesting ways. In this paper, four case studies will be used to explore the ways in which such new frames are created. The notion of ‘theme’ is adopted from hermeneutic phenomenology to describe and understand the subtle ways in which designers navigate the area between problem and solution space during framing.

Keywords: frame - problem solving - theme

INTRODUCTION

It is often said that expert designers look for ‘the problem behind the problem’, investigating the initial framing of the problem situation [Schön, 1983]. The ability to reframe the initial problem situation is widely seen as a key design skill, and it is central to the claim that design thinking can contribute to radical innovation in other fields.

Yet there are few studies that seek to describe and understand this process in detail. In this paper we will use four extensive case studies of complex design projects done within the context of the NSW Designing Out Crime centre to support an investigation into the framing behaviour of expert designers. We find that new frames tend to arise from the intimate engagement of the designer with the ‘themes’ of key stakeholders. The case studies suggest that the designers identify these themes in the periphery of the problem situation.

CREATING FRAMES

Although frames (in the definition of a specific viewpoint, a ‘seeing- as’ that has the potential to lead to the creation of solutions) can sometimes be paraphrased by simple and elegant (metaphorical) statements, they are actually quite complex and subtle thought-tools. They are also often implicit, vague, and they can contain internal contradictions. In the book ‘Design Expertise’, Bryan Lawson explained the complexities of framing by reiterating the example of the architect Richard MacCormack’s acclaimed chapel at Fitzwilliam College in Cambridge [Lawson, 2004, 2009]. The original brief was to design a modern chapel that would in one of the courtyards at Cambridge University. The flow of ideas had led the team of experienced architects in the direction of creating a round worship space that would look as if it was be suspended in a square enclosure. This caused an acute set of problems for the design - how does one connect these very different forms? What is the nature of the relationship between these forms, and how can that be expressed through the detailing of the connection? After many what seemed to be fruitless hours of working on possible placings, formal solutions and construction principles, one of the designers realized that what they actually were creating was a ‘vessel’ (a boat!). This key framing statement created a whole set of implications that the architects and construction engineers could fruitfully pursue. The relationship between a boat and its surroundings (the quayside) is of course one of ‘mooring’ - and it is easy to imagine the kind of shapes that would help articulate that ‘mooring’ relationship between the suspended chapel and its enclosing building. The idea of a boat comes with a very rich language of shapes (e.g. railings) and construction principles (e.g. beautiful curved

wooden hull) that have been exploited in the final design. The immense richness of the boat metaphor means that the problem has shifted from a groping around for an organisational principle to one of exercising restraint, not to take the 'boat' metaphor too literal and end up with kitsch.

What's in a frame?

A frame is an organizational principle, a more or less coherent set of statements that are good to think with, that can inspire a course of action. Framing as an activity mostly appears when a deadlock or paradox is encountered in the course of a design project. The proposing of a new frame includes the use of certain concepts, which are assigned significance and meaning (Tannen, 1986). These concepts are not neutral: they have the potential to start leading the designer's perceptions further on in the process of creation. The creation of a frame is the result of a broader intentional action, the frame then re-articulates the scope of that intention in new and interesting ways. Frames should also be actionable, have the possibility to lead to solutions. While frames can be fairly abstract statements, they are situated in the sense that they are custom-made for the (action) context of the problem at hand.

For a frame to be effective it really has to be inspiring and captivating, come 'alive' within a design project and immediately lead to mental images in the key people involved. A frame is also a social entity. Yet communication of frames is not an easy matter, even among experienced designers that have collaborating for years and years (Valkenburg, 2000). The problem seems to be that frames are only fruitful when they are really adopted by the other team members, as an active way of thinking. Thus one cannot communicate a frame by just blurting it out - if the team members are thinking from another perspective, they probably won't know what the designer with the frame idea is talking about. It is also not very productive to argue about a frame as being the right one: the frame is only going to be 'right' if the team members find it inspiring and can use it as a lead for their own mental structuring of the situation. Thus in the Delft Protocol Studies (Cross et al, 1996) we can observe how in trying to communicate a frame that has dawned upon one of

the designers, we can almost see him bite his tongue, and resort to very long sentences that are much more abstract the preceding conversation. The designer suggests the frame for adoption, and seeks to do so by leading the other designers to have the same frame idea themselves. Through these vague suggestions the designer possibly tries to bypass the adoption problem: people will almost automatically adopt their own ideas. The sentences he uses in this subtle process of roundabout suggestion easily contain 40-60 words or more, while in other episodes of the same protocol the design conversations within this experienced team tended to be in short, snappy sentences.

Then there is the issue of the qualities of frames. While frames are content-statements, and hence completely depend on the problem situation at hand, they do possess generic qualities that are worth keeping in mind. Good frames ideally manage to create an image that spans and integrates a broad range of issues under consideration, and perhaps draws in even more from outside the core problem arena. Good frames are coherent, and provide a stable (largely non-contradictory) basis for further thinking. Good frames are also really robust in a social sense, in that the image they conjure up in the minds of the designers and stakeholders are sufficiently similar to provide a 'common ground' for the discussion of the problem, as well as possible solutions. Of course good frames need to be inspiring and original - perhaps not completely new-to-the-world, but at least new to the problem setting. And good frames can be thought-provoking and lively, engaging people to adopt the framework and invite them to think along in the proposed direction.

Frames can often be episodic, in the sense that they are labels that trigger mini-stories, opening up a whole world of shared experiences among people. With those stories comes the episodic, integrative knowledge that is needed as the basis for solution ideas [Lawson, 2009]. Design practitioners are storytellers, capturing the elusive aspects of their profession by talking about projects. There is a danger in this, as confabulation and hyperbole that are great for spicing the stories to entertaining the

audience might slip unnoticed into the mix of accepted truths.

FRAMING IN PRACTICE: THE DESIGNING OUT CRIME CENTRE CASES

To investigate the framing behavior of expert designers we will now introduce some case studies of design projects that were executed within the framework of the New South Wales Designing Out Crime centre over the last three years. But first we will sketch something on the background of the centre, to give a sense of the contexts of these case studies.

In 2007 the New South Wales government's Department of Justice and Attorney General and the University of Technology Sydney took the initiative to establish a Designing Out Crime research centre. Its remit is to use design practices as a starting point for revolutionizing the way we are dealing with the need for safety and security in society. Since its inception, the DOC centre has developed several approaches for dealing with the very broad area of safety and security, and delivered around 50 projects. These range from the development of technical solutions to prevent the stealing of satellite navigation systems from cars to proposals for the redevelopment of public spaces and social housing areas. Central to the DOC approach is the pledge to - wherever possible - avoid the creation of 'countermeasures' to crime. These countermeasures inadvertently remind us of the occurrence of crime - in the end making us more fearful and wary. This climate of fear destroys the open-minded interchange between people from different backgrounds that creates the social fabric of our society.

Within the practices of the DOC centre, the framing of the issues is the main and absolutely crucial step. It is important to realize that the many projects the DOC centre has taken on are in a sense all based on 'old' problems. The partner organizations that are involved in these projects have already been trying to deal with these issues for a very long time. But somehow these particular problems have proven impervious to their conventional problem solving strategies. Prevalent problem solving strategies in the area of safety and security are very focused on the creation of countermeasures, with parties often

resorting to 'strong arm tactics' of creating more rules to force people's behavior away from unfortunate patterns, and the strengthening of law enforcement. Countermeasures abound, either through putting up defenses (putting up fences) or improving the information gathering through the introduction of CCTV camera systems to help 'solve' crime after it has happened. There is a subfield within criminology, Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED), that is set up to create design rules for public places to make them safer and less amenable to criminal activity (Cozens, 2005; Clarke, 1992). While the rules that are proposed in this field are deceptively simple, applying them in a complicated real-world situation turns often out to be a real challenge. The field of Designing Out Crime deals with extremely complicated design situations. In its projects, the Designing Out Crime centre is careful to take a real-life context as its starting point, and develop situated solutions - many of these could be applied much more widely, but their core strength comes from having been developed for a specific and concrete situation. We will see that this concentration on the concrete situation is absolutely crucial for the creation of new frames in this area.

At the core of the DOC centre's practice are five key activities: research, initiation, framing, design exploration and handover. In its initial **research**, DOC uses criminological data and broader psychological and sociological studies. Its own research concentrates on auxiliary studies that is necessary to create a clear and detailed picture of the precise situations and scenarios that a DOC project might intervene in. Then DOC **initiates** project around problem areas. In many cases there is not one clear or dominant 'problem owner' around a crime area, DOC organizes meetings and seminars to get the possible stakeholders around the table. DOC also initiates speculative projects on its own, then using the project outcomes as a way to get the relevant parties around the table. DOC's core activity is the **renewed framing** of the issues. The creation of a new and interesting viewpoint creates the possibility to bring problematic situations forward. Then DOC moves into a design phase, where student groups explore possible design solutions to

the reframed problem. This is **design exploration** is a crucial component of the DOC approach, as it allows a check that the reframing actually has the potential could lead to realistic results, and it creates a wealth of material mapping out possible futures for the partner organizations. The DOC centre's primary involvement ends with a **handover**, of the project results to the partner organizations.

ENTERTAINMENT QUARTER

The continuous problems in an entertainment quarter of a big city (attracting 30,000 young people every Friday and Saturday night) include drunkenness, fights, petty theft (pickpocketing) and drugs related crime. The countermeasures that have been taken over the years have created a slightly grim environment, and don't seem to help much in preventing crimes and anti social behavior. Increasing the police presence beyond the current level is not an attractive option.

Designers from the DOC centre quickly reframed the issues that were presented as law-and-order problems, into the question how this area could be decriminalized. These are young people wanting to have a good time, not hard core criminals. But a crowd of 30,000 young people, that could be compared to a good-sized music festival - just the fact that it happens twice a week is neither here nor there. To take this analogy further: what would you organize if you were organizing a music festival? A well-run music festival would provide lots of facilities that have not been taken care of in the entertainment quarter at all, but that could easily be designed in.

For one thing, when organizing a music festival one would make sure that people would be able to get there, and also leave again when they wanted. In this entertainment quarter, the peak time of young people coming into the area is about 1AM, and the last train leaves at 1.20... Getting a taxi takes about 2 hours in the middle of the night, if the taxi driver wants take you at all (taxis have begun to avoid this area). So once you are in the entertainment quarter you are basically crammed into a single road until the trains start running again at 6 in the morning. That is ultimately very boring and frustrating. Apart from the obvious improvement of putting in more trains, the DOC designers proposed as a fall back

position a system of temporary signage on the pavement, helping the party-goers to get to a different train station (20 minutes walk) that has trains running throughout the night.

In organizing a music festival, one would also create chill-out spaces and continuous attractions, to make sure that people can move around, and that their experience does not completely depend on what happens on a single big stage. As it happens, this entertainment quarter has a few big clubs that form the main attractions. As a result, youngsters that have visited a club and go back out on the street might find that the queue for the next one is several hours long. If they decide not to join the queue, they are out in the streets again with nothing to do. The DOC designers proposed that is problematic pattern of behavior can be minimized by providing a texting service or a smartphone app, so people can find out how long the wait for the next club is before leaving the one they are in. Some of the laneways around the central street can be opened up as rest areas, with water fountains and a relaxed atmosphere away from the crowds.

An obvious thing one would organize for a music festival is to provide enough public toilets. This particular entertainment quarter has only three, one of which not much used because it is located at the Police station. Consequently here is a real street urination problem. The DOC designers proposed using a system of mobile toilet blocks.

Over the years, the clubs have hired more and more security personnel and bouncers as part of the conventional approach to solving the alcohol related crime and anti-social behavior issues. The DOC designers proposed a system of very visible young 'guides' in bright T-shirts, that help people find their way through the area and that are also approachable when help is needed. These bright and cheery Info people create a social environment, instead of the dark uniforms of the huge Private Security firm men in black that lurk in every corner - a major contribution to the grim atmosphere of the area.

The two key events in this DOC project that led to the successful reframing were the decision not to take the issues like they were presented, as crime problems, and then the emergence of the 'music

festival' analogy. Once the problems were framed in this way, solution proposals started flowing freely.

RETAIL THEFT

Shoplifting is quite a common crime, costing consumers billions of dollars worldwide every year - retailers have learnt to calculate in about 5% of what they euphemistically call 'shrinkage'. Conventional measures to reduce shoplifting include the use of mirrors and CCTV cameras, the installing of warning signs and the hiring of additional security staff. Evidently shop design also can play a major role in preventing this crime, but this is where retailers and their retail designers face a strange paradox: to sell, the goods need to be displayed in a beautiful and tempting manner - and they need to be easily accessible for prospective customers. Most shopowners reject any design intervention that would lead to a drop in legitimate sales, and rather live with the 'shrinkage'. Yet there is a societal cost to shoplifting that has to be taken into account: it is often an easy 'first crime' for youth. If it isn't nipped in the bud, the habit of stealing can easily lead to them getting involved in other, more serious crimes. DOC researchers and designers were faced with the challenge to create solutions that would not decrease the attractiveness of the merchandise (increase it if possible), while preventing it from being stolen. In the DOC project these issues were quickly focused on a number of goods that get stolen a lot - the list includes small expensive items like cosmetics, but also batteries, clothing and cans of baby formula. The designers quickly realized that the bigger thefts occurred when there was a black-market network in place where goods could be sold on easily. They decided to concentrate on these, and frame the problem as one of preventing large quantities of these goods to be stolen, (often by simply slipping products off the shelf into an open bag (Figure 1)). This frame takes the problem away from complete prevention, which is very hard to achieve without making life harder for the legitimate customers, and led to many solutions for a broad range of products and situations. For baby formula, for instance, the designer came up with a dispensing mechanism that only allows you to take out one can at a time - preventing a thief to sweep an armful into his or her bag. The wheels of the dispenser are

filled with sand that makes a gentle but persistent sound, which allows shop attendants to take a look when that sound is heard persistently.

Figure 1: Shoplifting made too easy.

In the case of cosmetics, the self depth was reduced, and the front of the shelf is replaced by a tilted panel with product information and advertising (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The new shelf design for cosmetics.

This barrier precludes thieves from just slipping the item into their bags, and forces an exaggerated arm motion that would attract attention if done time and time again. As soon as the customer reaches for the product, the panel and the product light up. This reminds those with a bad conscience that they have just activated a motion detector, while creating a better user experience for the trustworthy buyer.

COUNTER TERRORISM

Circular Quay, in the middle of Sydney, is a truly spectacular site. The beautiful views of the harbor are framed by the iconic Harbour Bridge and the Sydney Opera House. It is a picture-perfect destination for millions of visitors every year.

Unfortunately, these very properties also make Circular Quay an attractive target for a possible terrorism attack.

The DOC designers were asked to come up with proposals how such an attack might be averted, or the damage that it would do minimized. Initial investigations showed that it would be important to try and limit car access to certain areas of the site. The counter-terrorism experts, very much aware of this need, had already proposed to put in hundreds of bollards to this effect. The DOC designers realized that this would ruin the site and make life very difficult for everybody. They also realized that apart from the wonderful setting, the public spaces around Circular Quay were actually not that great - some large open squares with nothing much to do. They seized the opportunity, framed the problem situation and proposed a complete redesign of the area that would make it fulfill its potential of being a window to Australia. Putting in artworks, appropriate seating, planting Eucalypt trees from the different states, having a small informal open-air stage, if done to the proper specifications, all helps to prevent vehicle access. And it saves the site from the bollards. The designers also proposed to minimize the effects of an attack by reducing the peak-hour crowds in the area. Thousands of city workers take the train from the Circular Quay railway station that is centrally positioned above the ferry wharves. By relocating the entrances and exits to that railway station to either side of the wharves, these city workers wouldn't need to wrestle their way through the throngs of tourists that mull around in the middle of the area.

A much more concrete counter-terrorism product was developed for a railway company. Some years ago, the company has removed the garbage bins from the stations and platforms, in fear of a possible terrorist bomb. The growth of food outlets has resulted in a litter-rich environment at the station, and the wish from the railway company to somehow

re-introduce garbage collection. Initially DOC was requested not to design anything, but to assist in selecting one from the many existing bins available worldwide. Three categories of bins were identified. The first category was bins designed to contain lateral damage by deflecting an explosion upwards. Built from special materials, expensive and difficult to service this type of design was entirely unsuitable for the covered platforms found in a majority of city train stations. The second group involved design features that limited the type of objects that could be placed in them, significantly complicating cleaning operations. The third design group consisted of very basic components, usually comprising of a metal hoop fitted with a clear cylindrical plastic bag. While easy to clean and making sure that a weighty object such as a bomb would be difficult to conceal the design negated the objective of improving the visual appearance of the station.

Given that no existing bins were deemed to be appropriate DOC steered the discussion away from design features towards the broader issue of the station's operations. Reframing the issue in this way highlighted a new way into the problem arena. This was that should there be a suspicion that a bin contained a bomb it would result in a lengthy investigation and extended evacuation of the public thus paralyzing the entire transport system.

This change in viewpoint enabled both the railway company and police to perceive that the real crux of the issue was how a rubbish bin might affect their operations in the event of a bomb scare, and how a good design could aid their emergency procedures while a poor design would hinder them. Thus a design brief, unlike those of alternative options, focused on the primary issue of keeping the rail operations running smoothly while encompassing the more immediate concern of a bomb exploding on a rail station. The new brief lead directly to the bin's most innovative feature this is a narrow gap at the back to permit the insertion of X-ray panels to allow safe and fast examination of contents without movement of the structure or its contents thus avoiding triggering a bomb. This feature, together with others designed to allow fast inspection by station staff and police eliminated the need for lengthy evacuations of the station.

SOCIAL HOUSING

Social Housing authorities around the world traditionally were very much focused on the bricks and mortar side of their business, and not involved with their tenants at all - except for chasing up unpaid rent. Public Housing in Australia was no exception, during the boom years in the 1970's, large estates with housing blocks scattered in open green spaces sprang up in the outskirts of the major cities. The idea was that friendly communities would form as occupants mixed while they played and relaxed in the generous public open spaces. In practice these common areas became drinking venues for teenagers, dumping grounds for household waste and places to contract drug deals. External laundry blocks gave way to shooting up galleries, the floors littered with needles. At night some of these estates became no go areas for law-abiding tenants. The value of the housing stock went into a downward spiral while maintenance costs mounted due to vandalism and graffiti.

The traditional response to this crisis situation is to improve security with additional police patrols and CCTV, increase street lighting and introduce schemes for cleaning up graffiti quickly. DOC proposed framing the problem away from the immediate security concerns to bringing back a sense of pride and responsibility for the inhabitants. A key device in this process is to divide large estates into smaller, manageable well-defined precincts. Within these precincts DOC can work with tenants to foster ownership of their immediate surrounds by engaging them in a re-design process such as siting new pathways, selecting appropriate fencing, choosing plants and locating external lighting. The objective being to create an individual identity for each dwelling that incorporates carefully placed territorial fencing, defined entry points, suitable garbage management and sympathetic landscaping. Much of the public space surrounding the housing blocks can be reassigned as private residential land or, depending on demographic need, devoted to vegetable garden plots, small local playgrounds, or basketball hoops. The result is the tenants create an environment designed to match their needs and under guidance shape a safe and secure place in which to live. This project reframes a problem that

focuses on consequences (crime and vandalism) to a theme around personal aspirations, enabling a totally different design approach with many rich solution opportunities.

EXPLORING THEMES

All of the qualities of frames that we discussed earlier come to the fore in these cases - take the entertainment quarter example. The key framing metaphor ('a music festival') integrates a huge number of issues that happen throughout the area, during all different stages of a night on the town. The original statement takes the discussion away from one of criminality to one of misdemeanors of otherwise mostly innocent and fun-loving youth. The mental image of the music festival is a coherent one, in all its complexity, and it is robust in the sense that it is one that can be easily understood and will be sufficiently shared among stakeholders - many of whom will have experienced festivals first-hand, or have had to think about them as concerned parents. There might be differences in interpretation and in emotional response, but those can be the basis for a good discussion that will only enrich the imagery that the designers and other involved parties then have at their disposal for use in the creation of solutions.

We have to be careful and realize that a frame is not a completely static concept, it sits within the world of actions and intentions, and whether some statement or string of thoughts can be called a 'frame' is completely defined by its use: certain string of words is a frame when it is used as a frame. There are many different types of statements and clusters of statements that can be used as a frame in creative practice. This also means that once frames become accepted, they can become the context for routine action. In a sense, framing is an action, but the frame itself continuously recedes into the background when it is used to think with. Especially in organizations that are not naturally reflective, a statement that started life as an original frame can easily become accepted as the norm for future action, and recede into the role of problem context - that is where frames can turn into implicit received wisdom that will start to hold back new developments (Paton, 2010).

To understand this process of ‘framing’ in detail, we need to dig deeper. In the case studies we observed that these expert designers tended to first look for the core paradox that gave rise to the problematic situation, and then proceed by largely ignoring it. They seemed focus on everything but that problem, looking in the periphery for inspiration to develop new frames that provide avenues for tackling the problem situation in a different way, employing different strategies for exploring the broader problem context for clues how to tackle the central issues.

In the retail theft case study the designers sought to frame the problem situation away from its original setting of completely cutting out the stealing of all kinds of goods. By focusing on the specific problematic situations, the designers managed to propose a solution that actually improves the experience of the shopper, while making them harder to steal in any significant quantity. In the counter terrorism example of the bins for the railway station, the problem was shifted from focusing on precluding the placing of bombs in the bins, to focusing on countering the disruption caused by counter-terrorism measures. In the housing example the crime issues were reframed to take into account the broader issues of the expression of identity and ownership of the inhabitants, and the environment was redesigned to support people in these needs. Thus new frames and ideas arise from the intimate engagement with the broader life-worlds of key stakeholders.

What the expert designers are engaging in here is a subtle process of analysis that is very close to the methods used in the creation of phenomenological descriptions of ‘lived experience’. Just like the phenomenologists, they analyse the situation by discerning the ‘themes’ in the life world of the stakeholders. The term ‘theme’ as we use it here is a complex theoretical notion, adopted from the methodology that is associated with hermeneutic phenomenology (van Manen, 1990, p 89) - where the notion of themes is used as a stepping stone for creating well founded descriptions of ‘lived experience’. In phenomenology a theme is the experience of focus, of meaning. Its formulation is at

best a simplification but often more a labeling of a set of significant experiences - a labeling that is not directly linked to one specific observation, but seen to underlie many observations. Themes are in a sense a tool, a form of capturing the underlying phenomenon one tries to understand. Distilling themes from a complex situation is described as a process of insightful invention, discovery and disclosure.

In design practice we see that ‘themes’, that could (from a problem solving perspective) be judged peripheral to the central issue become the triggers for the creation of new frames, and help the designers to eventually create a solution that resolves the core paradox. Expert designers use their exploration of themes as a trigger, directing their creative imagination towards creating new frames. Although an important part of professional design practice, this is often a largely informal process. Designers talk quite loosely about ‘getting close’ to the situation, they talk about ‘richness’ in the problem area, and they do stress the importance of getting ‘first-hand experience’ of the problem situation. Once they get into the problem situation, they seemingly have no deliberate or systematic way of dealing with it. It looks as though they just hang around aimlessly, and just the notion that they are there would have to somehow fill their head with ideas. We would argue that they are actually observing clues that can lead to themes that will help them create a response to the problem situation. These clues are not explicitly expressed as themes, but often they are often packaged in episodic knowledge, as stories that together can give us some insight into their meta-practice. Two examples can illustrate this point.

An internationally renowned bag designer recounts how she goes to the market on Saturday to observe people handling the wares that they buy and the various ways they hold the bags they have brought, as they are getting heavier with every purchase. But her observations go way beyond these physical and functional aspects of carrying. She focuses on somebody and follows them around, looking at who they are (nervous? extraverted?), imagining how they live, and what they do in their life. The bags she

then designs have a real cleverness about them, and they are somehow curiously satisfying to use. They tend to have hidden tricks in them, allowing them to be worn in different ways. A small-looking elegant handbag can be expanded to hold A4 papers after all. A clever little bulge in one of her bags helps you not just bring your laptop, but also your apple to work (Van Eeghen, 2009).

The famous Japanese product designer Naoto Fukasawa describes how he makes video clips on the street, just observing how people use the city environment (Fukasawa, 2007). For example, there is a clip where he observes people on the platform of the Tokyo metro, pacing around while texting, using the profiled stripes on the pavement that are put there for the orientation of blind people to guide themselves around the pillars. A brilliant observation that doesn't just tell you something about the use of the affordances of these stripes, it conveys deeper insight into the state of mind of these commuters and how we navigate routinely through public spaces. Needless to say that understanding the behavior and deeper needs of commuters in this way can lead to many new ideas for improving their environment.

CONCLUSION

In the four Designing Out Crime case studies we can observe that the discerned 'themes', that could be judged peripheral to the central problem become the triggers for the creation of new frames, and help the designers to eventually create a solution that resolves the core paradox. In the examples above we have seen that expert designers investigate the broader set of themes at play in the problem situation (Lawson et al, 2009) in such a way that they work as a trigger, directing the creative imagination of the designers towards new frames.

The fascinating design practice of creating new frames based on the broader investigation of themes is analytical as well as creative. It is an intense form of sense-making that includes the creative act of giving meaning to some aspects of a complex reality over others. Van Manen aptly describes themes as the "knots in the webs of our experiences", partly found and partly made. Themes are ambiguous in

this respect - and that is reflected in the ambiguous status of that 'themes' have within design reasoning: as within hermeneutic phenomenology, they are meaningful elements of the situation, yet they are neither problem nor solution, but rather present a neutral ground that holds potential for development. They are on the cusp. All the projects that were described above have had that moment of suspension, of ambiguity and tension in them - where the original problem (as it was presented by the stakeholders) has receded into the background, and all the aspects in the complex problem situation are up in the air. They can then come together in new ways - that is how the new frames were formed.

The introduction of 'themes' within the vocabulary of design research will allow design researchers to create much closer descriptions of the hitherto elusive activity of frame-creation. It can feed into a deeper understanding of the subtle ways in which designers navigate the space between problem and solution. This could help to detail the general co-evolution model of conceptual design (Dorst et al, 2001).

These descriptions in turn could then lead the development of much more strategic ways of dealing with themes within design practice: designers and designing organisations could develop ways of deliberately, strategically, extending and moulding the repertoire of themes that feed into the frames that they create. As in hermeneutic phenomenology, we expect to find that the themes expert designers find/create in these design practices are often closely associated with deep human needs and existential issues (e.g. the need for the expression of identity, place-making, care, relationship to 'the other', etc). If these deep human needs are the ultimate underpinning for many themes, and thus for the creation of successful frames, further research is needed on the ways in which designers transform these deeper needs into frames within the context of the project at hand.

The ability to understand these deep human needs and to creatively deal with them in the context of theme-creation and reframing should be high on the agenda in the design curriculum of the future.

REFERENCES

- Clarke, R. (ed.) (2000) *Situational Crime Prevention: Successful Case Studies*. New York, Harrow and Heston.
- Cross, N.G. Christiaans H.H.C.M., Dorst, K.(eds) (1996), *Analysing Design activity*, Wiley, Chichester UK
- Cozens, P., Saville, G., Hilloer. D. (2005) Crime prevention through environmental design (CPTED): a review of modern bibliography, *Property Management*, Vol. 23, No. 5, 328-356.
- Dorst K. and Cross N.G. (2001) Creativity in the design process: co-evolution of problem-solution, *Design Studies* 22, page 425-437, 2001.
- Van Eeghen, H. Gannij, J. (2009) *Bag and shoe design* Hester van Eeghen, BIS, Amsterdam
- Fukasawa, N. (2007) *Naoto Fukasawa*, Phaidon Press Ltd, London UK
- Schön D.A. (1983) *The Reflective Practitioner: How professionals think in action*. London: Temple Smith, 1983
- Van Manen, M.(1990) *Researching Lived Experience*, 1990, The Althouse Press, Ontario
- Lawson, B. & Dorst K. (2009) *Design Expertise*, Architectural Press, Oxford, UK
- Lawson, B. (2004) *What Designers Know*, Architectural Press, Oxford, UK
- Paton, B., Dorst, K. (2010) Briefing and Reframing. *Proceedings of the Design Research Symposium 8 (DTRS8)*, 317-335.
- Tannen, D. (1986). Frames Revisited. *Quaderni di Semantica*, 7(1), 106-109.
- Valkenburg, R. (2000) *The reflective practice in product design teams*, Thesis TUDelft, The Netherlands